

SARAH – uSer-centred civil infrAstructure Reliable Assessment and Healing

Press Release

Grenoble, 15-09-2025

The SARAH project, „uSer-centred civil infrAstructure Reliable Assessment and Healing“ officially launched on 01-06-2025 to transform how Europe inspects, maintains and repairs its critical civil infrastructure.

SARAH adopts a human-centred, safe-by-design integrated digital solution that meshes metaverse technologies, sensors and digital twins with egocentric augmented reality. The platform guides civil infrastructure supervisors and invention teams through decision-making, planning, execution and reporting, while enhancing occupational safety and skill development on to the ground.

Key components include:

- Deployment of innovative on-site sensors (corrosion monitoring, force gauges for soil anchors, structural crack measurement)
- Unmanned aerial systems (up to 1 kg) for sensor deployment or interrogation for rapid, cost-effective issue detection, and for structure repair
- A real-time digital twin and a decision support engine ranking repair needs with 98% accuracy, enabling precise prioritisation of maintenance actions, and delivering an ad-hoc 80% correct, context-specific advice for inspection and repair risk assessment
- A
- Remote expert assistance and augmented reality guidance for field workers, achieving 80% user satisfaction in trials
- Automated, generative AI – driven certification reports produced post-intervention in at least two standardised formats
- Adoption of human-centric approaches over the entire development and lifetime of solutions

Coordinated by CEA-Leti, the SARAH consortium brings together leading industries, universities, research centres and technology providers from across Europe. Together, they will deliver a scalable, interoperable platform designed to extend the service life of viaducts, tunnels, ropeways and other civil structures while reducing maintenance costs and environmental impact. The project realizes principles on human-centred design and participative development of work and organisations, to have solution-based and systemic perspective to the digitalization - truly aligning human factors approach and aims of Industry 5.0 by EU.

„Preserving the value and safety of Europe’s civil infrastructure requires smarter tools – that’s where SARAH comes in. We are proud to contribute to this initiative aimed at transforming the infrastructure management across Europe, with economical and societal impacts“, says Sébastien Boisseau, Lab manager at CEA-Leti.

Figure 1: SARAH project consortium

Supported by a Horizon Europe grant of almost EUR 6 million over three years (01-06-2025 until 31-05-2028), SARAH is funded under the Digital, Industry and Space programme, fully aligning with the EU’s digital agenda and contributing to clean air, artificial intelligence and climate action priorities.

Further information can be found on the [project website](#) and [LinkedIn channel](#).

For media inquiries, please contact:

Mrs. Isabelle DOR:

SARAH Project Coordinator

CEA - French Alternative Energies and Atomic Energy Commission

Mrs. Ingrid Armengaud:

SARAH Communication Lead

Armengaud Innovate GmbH

Funded by the European Union under Grant Agreement No. 101178082. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Health and Digital Executive Agency (HADEA). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.